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Advantages And Constraints Of Integrating Human Security In Pakistan's Security Framework

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ABSTRACT

The study aims to explore the possible benefits and challenges of incorporating Human Security as new security paradigm in Pakistan. Using qualitative method with an interpretivist approach, the study conducted semi-structured in-depth interview of eight experts or academics in security studies to explore how the integration of human security framework in Pakistan's security landscape offers both advantages and challenges. The study analyzed the expert interviews using thematic analysis. Integrating the normative insights from the Human Security model (UNDP, 1994) and analytical perspective from the Copenhagen School's Securitization Theory (Buzan, Waever & de Wilde, 1998), the study found that the human security model offers a comprehensive and holistic approach, broadening the scope of security while helping reduce root causes of conflict and instability and promoting the image of the country as a stable and resilient state. The study found various challenges and constraints towards adoption of human security model as a security framework in Pakistan in shape of opposition from dominant policy makers and lack of resources.

Keywords: *Human Security, Securitization, Pakistan, Traditional and Non-Traditional Security, Security Challenges*

Introduction

Since its inception, Pakistan's national security discourse has been dominated by traditional security model, with a primary focus on territorial integrity, military strength and state sovereignty. The security policy of the country has revolved around external threats such as Indian aggression and recent frequent incursions by terrorists from Taliban-ruled Afghanistan. Consequently, the state has prioritized military strength and defense spending at the expense of other sectors such as health, education and socio-economic development. While in the face of external threats, such a state-centric security approach is arguably justified, the model has left other dimensions of human development inadequately addressed (Shah, 2021).

Along with external threats, Pakistan faces enormous challenges internally ranging from

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terrorism and extremism to widespread poverty, lack of access to basic amenities such as healthcare, education, food and clean drinking water. Unemployment, socio-economic disparities, corruption, inflation and weak governance have further exacerbated the internal security environment of the country. The widespread gender inequality and discrimination at work have contributed to further security hardships. The uncontrolled rise in population has been another major issue in term of security in the face of limited resources, employment opportunities and infrastructure. The bulge in population has led to increased social unrest and instability. The effects of climate change in shape of natural disasters, rising temperature and increased rainfalls affecting agriculture, water resources and livelihoods have had widespread impacts on the country economically exacerbating the existing vulnerabilities (Idrees, Ahmad & Riaz, 2024; Iqbal, 2024).

In the post-Cold War era, the concept of human security has undergone huge transformation, expanding beyond traditional security confined to territorial defense and military preparedness. This shift was first crystalized by United Nations Development Program (UNDP) in its widely known report 'Global Human Development Report' published in 1994, focuses on human-centric sectors, encompassing economic, food, health, environmental, personal, community and political security (UNDP, 1994). The concept emphasizes threats to individuals and communities are as menacing as unconventional threats. Consequently, integrating concept of human security as a security model in national security policy has emerged as a cornerstone of contemporary policy discourse across the globe. However, in Pakistan, the security discourse remains primary state-centric, under military influence, emphasizing military preparedness, territorial integrity and strategic competition justifiably due to internal insurgencies and regional rivalries. In the context, non-traditional threats highlight the inadequacy of traditional security framework in ensuring sustainable security and stability.

In this context, analyzing the advantages and limitations of integrating human security into Pakistan's security framework offers timely and essential insights. Such an analysis can contribute to redefinition and rethinking of Pakistan's security priorities which may balance traditional and non-traditional security threats.

Background and Review

In the modern age, most of the nation states have understood that adopting a people-centric approach than a state-centric approach offers a clear and effective roadmap to address various security concerns of a state. Scholars and analysts in the field of security studies (Duffield, 2006; Battersby & Siracusa, 2009; Duffield & Waddell, 2006; McGrew & Poku, 2007; Altman, Camilleri & Eckersley, 2020) are of the view that UNDP's 1996 model of human security is one of the best security models for a state and its citizens offering lots of advantages and roadmap towards stability and protection of all sectors of human interest. From environmental protection to socio-economic security, political stability, better health and education and transparent and accountable governance, human security sees protection and well-being of people more significant than a state by itself. In the case of Pakistan, scholars (Syed, 2014; Chauhdry, 2014; Gul, Asghar & Faraz, 2021; Naz & Akber, 2019; Shaikh, Khuhro & Kolachi, 2024) argue that adoption of traditional security framework by Pakistan in the face of external threats mainly from India and Afghanistan is justified; however, the traditional security framework fails to prioritize other sectors such as widespread poverty, economic disparities, political instability and illiteracy which fuel terrorism, extremism and organized crime within the country. Therefore, they argue that a more inclusive approach in the shape of human security framework which prioritizes human development,

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Pakistan can prioritize both external and internal threats equally while making policies to address them on the equitable basis.

Khan, Jaspal & Yasmin (2017) argue that the current national security policy lacks a balance between the security of state and security of its citizens. Explaining the constraints, they argue that Pakistan's geo-strategic location and world powers' active politics in the region over their interests along with US-China new Cold War, India's hegemonic intention, uncontrolled developments in Afghanistan and other strategic reasons, Pakistan's focus has been towards securing its border and territorial integrity while overshadowing non-traditional security. Abbas & Cheema (2022) argue that until announcement of 'National Security Policy of Pakistan (2022-2026) in 2022, Pakistan never had a publicly declared document or policy regarding its national security. Though the first national security document is regarded as citizen-centric; however, it lacks a clear roadmap towards addressing the underlying cause of conflict or insecurity. Besides this, they argue that the implementation of the mentioned reforms is headed by traditional security institutions which means that the traditional thinking or working has not changed which becomes a significant hurdle in complete and successful implementation of the given reforms.

The concept of human security has gained wide significance in academia exploring its benefits, challenges and implementation as an alternative security model; however, benefits and challenges of adopting human security as an alternative model remain unexplored in Pakistan's context. Previous studies lack analysis regarding what benefits the human security model offers for Pakistan in the long term. Previous studies lack analysis regarding what factors limit the adoption and implementation of human security as security model in Pakistan. Therefore, the current study is an attempt to fill the above-mentioned gap by analyzing the potential benefits and practical challenges towards adoption and implementation of human security as a security model in Pakistan.

Theoretical Framework

The study integrates the normative insights from the Human Security model (UNDP, 1994) and analytical perspective from the Copenhagen School's Securitization Theory (Buzan, Waever & de Wilde, 1998). By facilitating a dual-analysis, the study understands security beyond state-centric lens by conceptualizing security beyond traditional thinking towards individual and societal well-being and examines the structural and institutional constraints by analyzing the political and institutional construction and institutionalization of security concerns. Using the lens of human security model, the study explores what benefits Pakistan can achieve by integrating human security into its security paradigm. Since, according to Securitization Theory, the concept of security is subjective with no universally accepted definition thus depending on any organized body to decide its concept (William, 2012), the study examines the structural and institutional conceptualization of security in the country which impede shift from traditional security to non-traditional security paradigm.

The dual-analysis provides a normative and conceptual basis for evaluating advantages of human security model and offers a conceptual framework to analyze political and institutional resistance which impede shift in security paradigm. The human security framework provides the rationale for redefining security policy towards human welfare while securitization theory explains the political and institutional barriers which impede this transformation.

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Method

Using qualitative method with interpretivist research approach, the study examines the interpretations and perceptions of experts regarding potential benefits and practical challenges of integrating human security in Pakistan's security framework. The qualitative method with an interpretivist research approach allows interpretation and understanding of the qualitative data. The study uses thematic analysis to identify, analyze and interpret themes across the qualitative data in shape of semi-structured in-depth interviews from experts in security studies. As suggest by Braun & Clarke (2013), the number of interviewees selected for in-depth interview are 8. Employing snowball sampling technique, the security experts, academics and individuals are selected based on their understanding and sufficient knowledge about the security situation in Pakistan.

The analysis of the qualitative data was carried out using Braun and Clarke's (2006) model of thematic analysis. Through inductive thematic analysis, the themes were determined by the researcher. The analysis started with reading all the data closely and repeatedly, identifying initial codes and patterns such as 'health', 'education' or 'budget', 'resources'. In the second step, keywords such as 'expanded security', 'focus on human needs' or 'soft power gain', 'international cooperation' were identified, helping identify further major themes from the data. In the third step, initial keywords were grouped into codes. For instance, keywords such as 'expanded security' and 'focus on human needs' were coded as 'from territorial to human' and 'soft power gain', 'international cooperation' were coded as 'recognition at international level'. In the fourth step, meaningful groups or initial themes from codes were identified. For instance, an initial theme namely 'expansion of concept of security' from the code 'from territorial to human' was identified. In the fifth step, themes were finalized and conceptualized through interpretation, defining the concepts which emerged out of the data. for instance, initial theme 'expansion of concept of security' was finalized as 'Broadening the scope of security'. In the sixth and final step, interpretation of the data as guided by the thematic analysis model was carried out, answering the questions raised in the study.

Analysis and Discussion

This section presents the analysis of the data collected through in-depth interview of experts in security studies, discussing the potential benefits and practical challenges of integrating human security model into Pakistan's security framework. Using Braun and Clarke's thematic analysis, the discussion links the identified themes to the study's theoretical framework, which combine the concept of human security and securitization theory, providing understanding regarding how integration of human security can broaden the concept of Pakistan's security framework and what structural and institutional barriers hinder its integration.

Security experts argue that some of the advantages of integrating human security model into Pakistan's security framework would be broadening scope of national security and the model's capacity in helping reduce the root causes of instability and insecurity and building an image of Pakistan as a stable and secure country globally. The analysis of collected data reveals that human security framework is a broad and comprehensive concept covering all domains of human life while providing a clear and effective roadmap towards addressing internal and external insecurities a country or nation faces. Therefore, its incorporation in the national security policy of Pakistan would help the country in securing not its borders but also its internal security while giving major emphasis and prioritization to protection and well-being of its citizens.

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Expansion of the Scope of Security

Experts outline one of the most significant advantages of incorporation of human security in Pakistan's security landscape would be its capacity in broadening the concept and scope of national security which is confined to only territorial integrity and military defense. Experts argue that embracing a more comprehensive understanding of security, human security as a security approach moves beyond traditional, state-bound and military-focused approach. Comparing the traditional state-centric security approach with non-traditional human-centric security approach, experts are of the view that traditional security approach has limitations and sidelines various important domains of human life while non-traditional human security approach covers all dimensions of security such as economic security, political stability, social well-being and environmental protection. According to them, non-military threats are not given any focus or priority in the traditional security paradigm thus lacking any comprehensive roadmap towards resolution of a conflict or insecurity in the long term. While on the other hand, they add, human security paradigm sees military and non-military threats as strong vulnerabilities in term of security of people and state. Adding more to the discussion, experts argue that traditional security approach aims to establish short-term security while human security approach offers a broader concept of security aiming to establish long-term security and stability by providing a roadmap towards addressing root causes of any conflict or instability. With a multi-dimensional approach, human security approach unlike traditional security approach aims to integrate all major sectors and domains to establish stability and long-term security.

The views from various experts reveal that human security as an alternative non-traditional security model has a broader scope and concept of security by encompassing all the domains of human life while aiming to address the complex and interconnected threats which may fuel insecurities and instabilities in a society. In the case of Pakistan, the experts are of the view that unlike traditional security approach which sidelines non-military threats, human security approach has the advantage of sharing a broader scope and concept of security covering all sorts of insecurities such as economic insecurity, political instability and environmental degradation. They argue that human security approach while helping reduce the root causes of insecurities recognizes that long-term peace and stability is possible when people are protected from all sorts of injustices, disease and insecurities.

Addressing the Root Causes of Insecurity

Experts argue that the incorporation of human security model into Pakistan's national security strategy will lead to reduction of the root causes of instabilities and insecurities prevalent in the country. With its focus on underlying issues such as poverty, inequality, health crisis, illiteracy, environmental degradation and marginalization, human security unlike traditional security approach provides a comprehensive and effective roadmap towards addressing the underlying causes of insecurity such as socio-economic disparities. The experts argue that non-state actors can easily exploit social vulnerabilities therefore until existing vulnerabilities are resolved, extremist and terrorist groups keep thriving. Experts note that by addressing economic and social inequalities, the state can create a more inclusive society, which may decrease internal conflicts and contribute to long-term peace and security.

Besides political benefits, experts see various social and economic benefits of incorporation of human security model in Pakistan's national security policy such as safety from environmental disasters, protection of livelihoods, increased crop production

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and increment of average lifespan by constituting health policies to mitigate risks. Examining the causes of insecurity such as economic disparity, poverty, marginalization and radicalization, experts argue that resolution of these underlying issues will lead to establishment of long-term peace and stability in the country.

Findings from previous studies (Mukhtar, 2018; Malik, Sandholzer, Khan & Akbar, 2015; Khan & Javaid, 2020; Ahmed, Yousaf & Zeb, 2018) align with arguments advanced by experts, noting that the root causes of instability and insecurity in Pakistan are deep and systematic while the nature of causes range from political to economic, social and environmental factors. The existing literature show that some of the major causes are poverty, marginalization, political instability and poor governance, human rights violations by state institutions, resource scarcity and destruction due to environmental degradation and indoctrination and radicalization. The studies argue that until the underlying causes are addressed, no stability and security can prevail in the country in the long term.

Enhancement of Pakistan's Global Standing

Experts who were interviewed are of the view that Pakistan's global standing is very low in almost all domains ranging from economy to environment, press, governance, security and human rights. They argue that Pakistan falls very low as per the international standards of development and safety. From press freedom to human rights, governance and economic and political stability, Pakistan possesses a very low index. Seeing these challenges, experts highlight the relevance of human security model in Pakistan's national security policy. Recommending the incorporation of human security approach in Pakistan's national security framework, experts argue that its incorporation has the advantage of building and improving the image and standing of Pakistan globally as the given security model focuses on addressing the underlying issues due to which country's global image and standing stands low.

With the resolution of the underlying issues such as political instability, economic crisis, environmental degradation, poverty, unemployment, low standards of living and rising growth in population, Pakistan can improve its global standing as a stable and developed country. They argue that incorporation of human security model enhances Pakistan's global standing by aligning with international humanitarian standards, boosting its reputation as a nation committed to human development and safety. Experts argue that incorporating human security into Pakistan's national security strategy can yield significant benefits, including enhanced stability, improved socio-economic conditions, increased citizen participation, and strengthened international relations. By focusing on the well-being of its citizens, Pakistan can build a more resilient and prosperous nation. As Pakistan is globally known as an insecure, unstable and under-developed country, experts see the current traditional security model doesn't offer any roadmap for improvement of Pakistan's image on the global stage.

Arguments advanced by experts are substantiated by previous studies. For instance, Nye (2019) explains the power of soft power by arguing that the use and status of power have changed and soft power has gained more status and strength than hard power. He argues that presently states and nations are known for their soft power that how much they are culturally, socially, economically and politically developed and stable. While arguing how states improve their image, Benoit (2020) explains that a country cannot restore its image rather improve it through public and cultural diplomacy while internally gaining economic and political stability. In the case of Pakistan, Khan (2020) argues that due to internal challenges in shape of terrorism, economic crisis, absence of rule of law and

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instable governance, Pakistan's global image has been badly tarnished therefore its standing is very low in most of the indexes such as press freedom, human development index, corruption index, human rights index, governance index and passport ranking. For instance, despite having given lots sacrifices against war on terror, it has been propagated that Pakistan supports terrorists by giving them safe heavens. Thus, he argues that Pakistan needs to counter such propaganda and improve its image. Besides this, Syed, Ahmad & Bhutta (2019) argue that culturally and historically Pakistan is a rich country and through showcasing its culture and history, Pakistan can improve its image. Substantiating the arguments made by the experts, the prior studies acknowledge the importance of internal stability and development for enhancement of Pakistan's image globally.

Constraints of Incorporating Human Security into Pakistan's Security Landscape

The experts who were interviewed share various constraints towards incorporation of human security model or implementation of its principle in the national security policy of the Pakistan. They argue that some of the main obstacle or challenges are resistance from traditional security institutions or their thinking to significant shift in traditional policy-making. Besides the resistance from policy-makers, they outline limitation of resources or budgetary constraints is one the major challenges to incorporate or implement human security model and its principles in Pakistan national security policy. Furthermore, they note that political instability and bad governance is another obstacle towards its incorporation and implementation. Lastly, they outline lack of political will constraining the incorporation and implementation of human security model in Pakistan's national security policy.

Previous studies also mention same obstacles. For instance, Khan, Jaspal & Yasmin (2017) argue that the current national security policy lacks a balance between the security of state and security of its citizens. Arguing the constraints, they argue that Pakistan's geo-strategic location and world powers' active politics in the region over their interests along with US-China new cold war, India's hegemonic intention, uncontrolled developments in Afghanistan and other strategic reasons, Pakistan's focus has been towards securing its border and territorial integrity while overshadowing non-traditional security. Abbas & Cheema (2022) argue that until 2022 when it 'National Security Policy of Pakistan (2022-2026)', Pakistan never has a publicly declared document or policy regarding its national security. Though the first national security document is regarded as citizen-centric; however, it lacks a clear roadmap towards addressing the underlying issues of the country which fuel conflict or insecurity. Besides this, they argue that the implementation of the mentioned reforms is headed by traditional security institutions which means that the traditional thinking or working has not changed which becomes a significant hurdle in complete and successful implementation of the given reforms.

Persistence of Traditional State-Oriented Security Thinking

Interview with experts of security studies agree that since the inception, Pakistan persists with a military and state-centric security policy, prioritizing territorial integrity and military defense over nation-building. Given its geopolitical location and challenges along with security concerns from India and Afghanistan, experts see Pakistan's security policy's prioritization of military security justifiable; however, they add that internal security threats and human development and security cannot be neglected in the face of external threats. They agree that in the face of traditional security's dominance in the

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policy-making process, space for a significant shift towards human security is limited. Due to emphasis on defending borders, nuclear deterrence, counter-terrorism and external threats, other domains have remained neglected. In the face of given issues and challenges, they argue that a major shift in national security policy remains challenging. The resistance from traditional security institutions and entrenched interests require significant shifts in thinking and policy-making which experts believe is a long way to go. They lament that due to the history of the country and its hostile neighbors, it is unlikely that human security would be accentuated.

Experts argue that since the Cold-War period, Pakistan's security policy has been weapons-based security measures believing in resolution of all security threats through use of weapons and military power. Experts examine the national security discourse that how military has been dominating the institutions and all spaces where policies are made and implemented and the traditional policy-making mindset has been successful in ratifying a discourse based on military defense and strength. Pakistan's major share of budget and resources are spent on military to defend country's borders and counter external and internal threats to security. The long-standing focus on traditional state-centric security not only limits the space for shift in national security policy but also neglects social development by diverting the major share of resources to military-centric security policy. The overall argument reveals that military and state-centric traditional security policy remains a vital and potential challenge towards adopting a human-centric security approach which focuses and aims to divert attention and resources to social development rather than military and defense. Besides this, the viewpoints shared by experts reveals that while having major influence in the country's political, economic and security direction, the military may not approve a complete shift in national security policy in the near future. Furthermore, the experts remind that the persistent threats such as terrorism, border disputes and emergence of Taliban justify the traditional security policy while also limiting the space for shift in security policy. In the face of given issues, traditional security policy may not change while it may include or incorporate some principle from human security paradigm in the existing national security policy of the country.

The previous studies substantiate the arguments advanced by experts. For instance, Hussain (2021) notes that the over-emphasis on traditional security threats has been the over-riding concern of the decision-makers. Ali (2023) adds that since the independence, having ruled the country for almost half period, military has been dominating policy-making in major sectors such as defense, security policy, foreign policy and internal security policy through direct or indirect rule. Due to its dominance, decisions and policies are made with military's approval. In another study, Ali (2021) argues that Pakistan's foreign and security policy has been deeply influenced by its concerns about India and as a result, nation-building has been overshadowed by territorial integrity and military defense. He states that the military has been making all the strategic decisions related to foreign and security matters. He laments that despite dominating the policy-making process, the country is still insecure from all fronts. He concludes that having dominance in the security, economic, political and diplomatic direction of the country, the military persists with a military-centric national security approach.

Financial Constraints

Experts who were interviewed argue that economic constraints limit the space for shift in security paradigm from traditional to human security approach because effective implementation of principles of human security require substantial resources and

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finances. Besides this, high expenditure in military and defense due to frequent incidents of terrorism and border tensions also create budgetary constraints to allocate funds for human development. Development sectors such as education, healthcare and social services have remained overshadowed by other priorities. Experts argue that there is a small allocation of funds for human development sector; however, with this small sum of budgetary allocation, no human development can be achieved for long term. Furthermore, a major sum of annual budget is spent on paying the foreign and local debt taken by the government. Inflation, unemployment, widespread poverty, low tax collection, untaxed economy and lack of investment in human development and security sector such as education and healthcare are other some issues which constrain the space for incorporation of human security model into Pakistan's national security model. Experts see it a major setback for Pakistan and its citizens that human security development and security sector has been neglected. The impact of not investing in education, healthcare and social welfare has been rise in insecurity in shape of social unrest and crime.

The overall discussion sees financial constraints as a significant challenge to Pakistan's transition from traditional security paradigm to human security paradigm. The discussion reveals that government's lack of capacity to invest in healthcare, education and social welfare has led to other instabilities and insecurities in shape of social unrest and crime. The argument reiterates that wellbeing of citizens relies on government's ability in term of enough resources and finances to prioritize human security and development.

Views of experts are corroborated by previous studies (Anwar, Abbas & Ashfaq, 2017; George, 2023; Hashmi, 2017; Hanif & Sultan, 2024) which note that Pakistan is economically a very weak and unstable country with rising inflation, widespread poverty, high rate of unemployment and low income. The previous analysis (Chauhdry, 2014; Mukhtar, Ishaque & Malik, 2019; Shirazi, 2016; Ghazanfar, Khalid & Qazi, 2022) argue that in the face of financial crunch and economic crisis, a complete or minor shift towards human security model from traditional security approach is challenging because a shift in security policy requires substantial resources to work on human development and security.

Political Instability and Bad Governance

Experts link human development and security with good governance and political stability arguing that political instability and ineffective governance is a major barrier toward shift from traditional security paradigm to human security approach. For a policy shift, they argue that a politically stable environment is required which Pakistan lacks, resulting in impediment of policy shift in the national security framework. Experts lament the frequent military coups, regime changes, weak mandate amidst political engineering and intervention by the establishment, systematic corruption, lack of accountability and misallocation of resources while arguing that due to the given issues, development and security concerns of citizens have been neglected. Furthermore, erosion of public trust and weak institutional capacity to resolve public concerns is a major challenge in term of governance and stability. They argue that Pakistan faces weak governance structures with poor coordination among various ministries and departments. They note that local governments which may prove vital for implementing measures related to human security remain underdeveloped and under-resourced. They institutional weakness, experts agree, limits the practical integration of human security principles into Pakistan's current national security policy. Overall, the experts see ineffective governance, absence of rule of law, weak mandate and diversion of resources to other

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domains as challenges towards socio-economic development in the country. Experts note that the lack of prioritization to socio-economic development in the country is due to rulers' focus on maintaining their own power and survival. When their focus is on their own power and privilege, public concerns remain unattended. The overall discussion links socio-economic development with good governance and a stable political environment where there is rule of law and accountability.

The views articulated by the participants align with findings from previous studies. For instance, Hassan & Zeb (2021) argue that socio-economic development has been badly affected due to political instability, bad governance and systematic corruption in the country. Khan (2021) links human development with effective governance, political stability, rule of law, absence of corruption and accountability arguing that due to lack of above-mentioned requirements for socio-economic development, Pakistan ranks low in human development index. Thus, the studies suggest that without political stability and effective governance, socio-economic development becomes challenging for a country to achieve.

Implication of Human Security–Securitization Theoretical Framework

The findings of the study resonate strongly with the core assumptions of Human Security paradigm and Securitization Theory, providing a comprehensive analytical lens for understanding the potential benefits and challenges of integrating human security model in Pakistan's security policy. The dual theoretical framework allowed expanding the concept of security itself while deconstructing the dominance of state-centric security discourse. The dual analysis enabled the study to examine forms insecurities in the country and how the given insecurities remain marginalized. The dual approach helped identify normative value of incorporating human security model and expose the structural and discursive barriers rooted in Pakistan's historically militarized and state-centric security discourse. The analysis combined with human security concept and securitization theory linked human-centered policy imperatives with the political processes which shape security agendas, offering understanding of potential benefits and limitations of integration of human security model in the country. The implication of dual theoretical framework extend beyond academic analysis to practical policymaking, urging a propound transformation of national security policy with protection of people as the foundation of the state's security.

Conclusion

The study discussed the potential benefits and practical constraints of incorporating human security model in Pakistan's national security policy. The study argues that integration of human security framework in Pakistan's security landscape offers both advantages and challenges. The advantages which the study discussed are the model's capacity of being a comprehensive and holistic approach while broadening the scope of security, helping reduce root causes of conflict and instability and promoting the image of the country as a stable and resilient state. The challenges to integration of human security model as a security framework in Pakistan are opposition from dominant policy makers, lack of required resources and ineffective governance and political instability. While arguing why Pakistan ranks low in term of human development index and socio-economic development, the study explains various causes such as absence of rule of law, frequent military coup, weak institutions, lack of stable political environment and effective governance, absence of accountability and transparency, weak mandate of elected government and widespread systematic corruption in public institutions. The

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study establishes that until the given issues and challenges are addressed, space for socio-economic development in the country remains limited which affect state and its citizens in the long term.

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